

Evaluating the Empirical Support for Cultural Intelligence Theory in International Business

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Abstract:

The cultural intelligence theory (CQ) is an important contemporary perspective for global business success. However, to some scholars, the definition of CQ remains confusing with inadequate empirical testing to its operationalization in the international business context. This paper aims at evaluating the empirical support for the Cultural Intelligence theory (CQ) in the international business (IB) context. The paper also sheds light on the multidisciplinary nature of CQ research and answers deeper questions, i.e., what leads to higher CQ, where CQ is most and least supported and among CQ dimensions, which one has the greatest and least effect on which dependent variable. Following a replicable and rigorous systematic review method, the paper examines a total of 222 empirical tests from 53 articles in the international business context. The total support for CQ as an independent variable was 74% while the most tested dependent variables were 'professional performance,' 'general adjustment,' 'work adjustment,' and 'interaction adjustment.' Levels of support for CQ effects on these variables were 59%, 83%, 68% and 78% respectively.

Keywords: Cultural Intelligence; International Business; Systematic Review; Performance; Expatriates Adjustment; Multinational Corporations.

Introduction

At the dawn of the new millennium, a contemporary stream of research has emerged concerning a new notion, 'cultural quotient' or as referred to hereafter, 'Cultural Intelligence' (CQ). The seminal work of Earley and Ang (2003) 'Cultural intelligence: Individual interactions across cultures' developed a CQ *construct* based on three dimensions of capabilities -cognitive, motivational and behavioral. Soon enough the notion of CQ became ubiquitous across several disciplines. At the time of finalizing this paper, the number of search hits that raised the phrase "cultural intelligence" in their titles was (952). However, as much as the CQ theory gained popularity, it also received harsh criticism, skepticism, and doubt.

While Bucker et al. (2015) demanded further attention to CQ operationalization and conceptualization, Johnson et al. (2006: 537) stated that CQ "appears to be concerned more with acquiring and practicing appropriate behaviors than with applying them in real-life situations." There were also a number of other skeptical scholars who tried to develop their own measurement tools (i.e., Moon 2010; Yitmen 2013; Bucker et al. 2015; Alon et al. 2016; and Lima et al. 2016). At the theoretical level, more criticism came from Dutta and Dutta (2013: 254) who argued that CQ as a 'Eurocentric' tool "emerged within the discursive spaces of cross-cultural management studies." They devoted their theoretical paper to "critique the discursive moves through which CQ is presented as a competitively advantageous tool for global organizations, deconstruct its theorization and measurement, and discuss its role in perpetuating transnational hegemony" (Dutta and Dutta 2013: 241). In a rather sarcastic fashion, Blasco et al. (2012: 230) compared training people to adapt to any context in international business to training them to *fly*. The authors went on questioning the very existence of the concept, concluding that "CQ has so far been only scantily tested empirically in terms of cultural *unintelligence*, making it at best useful as a hypothesis" (Blasco et al. 2012: 242).

On the other hand, Ang et al. (2007: 336/ 240) claimed that their new "culture-free" construct "should provide a systematic rationale for organizing

and integrating existing research on intercultural competencies." They also introduced a 'metacognitive' dimension and developed a 20-item measurement scale CQS to empirically test the theory. In their detailed review, Alon and Higgins (2005: 509) concluded that while the 'Analytical Intelligence' (IQ) and the 'Emotional Intelligence' (EQ) are important for business leadership success, the 'Cultural Intelligence' (CQ) is essential for *global* business leadership success. Further, according to Thomas et al. (2015), "the importance of understanding the effect of cultural differences on management behavior has never been greater."

What is intriguing about the above debate is that it could be endless with both sides either theoretically denounce the theory or partially assess it empirically. At the same time, while there were previous reviews that tried to capture the bigger picture (i.e., Thomas et al. 2008; Yitmen 2013; Matsumoto and Hwang 2013; Leung et al. 2014), none of them adopted a systematic empirical approach. Perhaps the common obstacle they all faced was the large volume of undifferentiated research in terms of quality, scope, and context. This paper aims at filling the gap by first differentiating CQ research then systematically assessing the empirical support for theory in the international business context. Does it aim at answering two main questions: to what extent CQ is researched in the international business context and to what extent it is supported empirically? While attempting to answer these two core questions, the paper will also shed light on deeper questions such as what leads to higher CQ, where CQ is most and least supported and among CQ dimensions, which one has the greatest and least effect on which dependent variable. But the following section will start by explaining the construct conceptualization and its four dimensions before clearly explaining the method and defend each step adequately. Finally, the results section will report and discuss the all findings before reaching a conclusion.

Cultural Intelligence

Grounded in the theory of multiple intelligences -introduced by Sternberg and Detterman (1986), "cultural intelligence is similar to, yet distinct from, other forms of intelligence" (Ang et al. 2007: 339). The authors embarked on a multidisciplinary research

“on psychometric models of intelligence and structure of human intellect” (Bhagat 2006: 289-90). While there were several research works that investigated ‘Inter-cultural Competencies’ (i.e., Paige 2004), ‘Cross-cultural Adaptability’ (i.e. Black and Stephens 1989), ‘Inter-cultural Effectiveness’ (i.e. Shaffer et al. 2006), and ‘Cultural Judgment’ (i.e. Einhorn and Hogarth 1981), it was the seminal work of Earley and Ang (2003) ‘Cultural intelligence: Individual interactions across cultures’ that developed a CQ *construct* based on three dimensions of capabilities -cognitive, motivational and behavioral and later added a fourth dimension, metacognition. The difference between CQ and the exhaustive list of cross-culture competences (3C) models is that the first is “culture-free” (Ang et al. 2007: 336). In other words, this type of intelligence can be utilized across deferent cultures.

To better explain the term ‘Cultural Intelligence’ it will be split into its constituents, ‘Culture’ and ‘Intelligence.’ The most famous definition of the first one is “the collective programming of the mind distinguishing the members of one group or category of people from another” (Hofstede 2001: 9). The word ‘programming’ may constitute two sets of rules, the *Dos* and *Don’ts*. Thus, cultures differentiate people because some of them will do or accept something and others will not. Intelligence, on the other hand, is “the mental abilities necessary for adaptation to, selection and shaping of an environmental context (Sternberg 1997a: 1036). Accordingly, intelligence is a set of different capabilities.

In plain English, CQ can be defined as the “person’s capability to adapt effectively to new cultural contexts” (Earley 2002: 274). But Thomas et al. (2008: 126), who synthesized most known definitions of CQ, defined it as a “system of interacting knowledge and skills linked by cultural metacognition that allows people to adapt to, select, and shape the cultural aspects of their environment.” However the most repeated definition in recent CQ literature remains the one introduced by Ang et al. (2007: 336), “an individual’s capability to function and manage effectively in culturally diverse settings.” For an in-depth review of CQ definitions and its dimensions dynamics, please refer to Thomas et al.

(2008) and Yitmen (2013). Further, CQ has four dimensions introduced by Ang et al. (2007: 338):

Metacognitive (CQ): Reflects mental processes that individuals use to acquire and understand cultural knowledge.

Cognitive (CQ): Reflects knowledge of the norms, practices, and conventions in different cultures.

Motivational (CQ): Reflects the capability to direct attention and energy toward learning about and functioning in situations characterized by cultural differences.

Behavioral (CQ): Reflects the capability to exhibit appropriate verbal and nonverbal actions when interacting with people from different cultures.

For example, a new Chinese expat in Germany with high CQ will think of strategies (metacognitive) to acquire the right knowledge about the local culture (Cognitive) and be internally motivated (motivational) to use this knowledge to exhibit appropriate behaviors when interacting with locals (behavioral).

Data and Method

“The systematic review is a process for reviewing the literature using a comprehensive preplanned strategy to locate existing literature, evaluate the contribution, analyze and synthesize the findings” (Saunders et al. 2016: 108). “Systematic reviews enable findings to be checked by readers... and are usually high-quality scholar works” (Greener 2008: 22). Most importantly, it allows “employing quantitative methods of evaluation [thus] synthesizing evidence in this method can be a powerful tool in building knowledge” (David and Han 2004: 42). While the systematic review originated in the medical sciences (Saunders et al. 2016: 108), recently, scholars in the international business discipline have also adopted the method. Among those are David and Han (2004) who evaluated the empirical support for the transaction cost economics (TCE) and Nijmeijer et al. (2014) who provided an integrative insight into the success of international franchises.

As a start, the review was meant to be as comprehensive as possible, but without the access to

all databases, the hard way of using Google Scholar (GS) was chosen. It is worth mentioning that Nijmeijer et al. (2014: 63) used eight databases - ABI/Inform Global, Cochrane Library, EconLit (EBSCO), Emerald, PsycINFO, PubMed/ Medline, Scopus and Web of Science. David and Han (2013: 43) used ABI/Inform Global and the EconLit (EBSCO) databases. However, there are some benefits to using GS to achieve high coverage.

Gehanno et al. (2013: 3) who tested GS to retrieve 738 references appeared in several systematic reviews -conducted using traditional academic databases, reported an “amazing” 100% coverage. They concluded “GS is highly sensitive, easy to search and could be the first choice for systematic reviews or meta-analysis. It could even be used alone” Gehanno et al. (2013: 4). Similarly, Brammer et al. (2016: 3) who used GS to check an outstanding number of references (4,795) from 120 systematic medical reviews against the original search results, reported *high* overall coverage (97.2%). The authors, however, stressed that GS does not allow viewing beyond the first 1000 results (Brammer et al. 2016: 6).

Further, Jacso (2008: 107) who tested an early beta version of GS pointed out several technical issues concerning the software itself, the repetition issue and the 1,000 thresholds. Based on the experience with other search engines, this issue -call it the giant search engine syndrome of 1k or ‘GSES’ for short- is common and not native to GS only. Finally, while Wu and Chen (2014: 376 and 385) confirmed that “academic communities have accepted Google Scholar over library metasearch tools... [they also] questioned the quality of documents retrieved”.

To sum up, GS will highly likely achieve the highest coverage, but bears the risk of GSES and does not differentiate quality research or repeated results. Yet with little options in hand, it was decided to go on with GS, benefitting from its coverage while figuring out solutions to its problems. GS database advanced search was first used on 18 April, and later towards the end of 2016 an update was carried out, typing the phrase “cultural intelligence” in the fields “with the exact phrase” and ticking the option “with all the words.” Then the phrase was chosen to occur only in the “title of the article.” Finally, the option

“Return articles dated between” 2007 – 2016 was used. The rationale was although the theory was originally introduced in 2003, a validated CQ scale was only available after 2007. Hence articles before that date are not useful for the empirical assessment.

The advanced search yielded 952 results, which kept us safe from GSES Syndrome. After excluding citations, there were 729 results. These formed the basic block of analysis and thus for easy reference, they were saved in 37 pdf files -each with 4 pages showing 20 results- except the last file that had 9. The next step was to manually exclude books and chapters of books from the list as GS did not provide this function although it had an option to choose only articles. The total number of books and chapters of books was 57 leaving us with a list of 672 titles. Next, to deal with repetitions, all titles were arranged in an alphabetically ascending list, and any repetition was deleted where the same article, i.e., an open access one might have been retrieved from different websites.

As expected there were 42 repetitions mostly duplicates and in one case a triplicate, which left 630 titles. Unexpectedly, it was interesting to have 4 incidences of another language, not English where the title was written in English but the text was in another language. There were also 10 incidences where the phrase “Cultural Intelligence” did not appear with the same words sequence although the option of showing “*the exact phrase*” was chosen. In these 10 cases, the words “Intelligence” and “cultural” appeared separately in the titles of the articles. This process left 616 articles. Please see figure 1 next that summarizes all the filters used in our systematic review.

The last step was to differentiate quality research. As mentioned earlier, this should be a prerequisite given the large volume of research and several critics concerning CQ operationalization in IB. Most importantly, it will also guarantee the quality of the empirical assessment. To achieve this, a rigorous condition was set, only articles published in subscription-journals will be considered. It should be noted that if an article appeared in a subscription-journal, but the article itself is an open access one, it was considered. For example, many

journals started offering recently what is known as ‘Green Access’ option where the author/s or a sponsoring body pays certain fees to allow free access to the article.

Figure 1: Systematic Review Filters

Besides following David and Han (2008: 51) in “selecting only published journals,” a number of specialized articles were also consulted to investigate the dilemma of open access vs. subscription journals. mainly because “the value and visibility of open access journals and the web citation counts have been prominent topics of debate in the library and publishing communities for many years” (Turk 2008: 71). For example, the open access journals “may have an incentive to publish many articles to boost revenue, lowering editorial standards if need be” (MacCabe and Snyder 2005: 457). On the other hand, “criticizing open access publishing is a bit like criticizing democracy (Osborne 2015: 637). However according to Osborne (2015: 637-8), “badly written papers, however easy to gain access to... actually,

hinder academic progress by diverting intellectual energy; their publication is irresponsible”. After all, “high- quality journals thus publish more good articles [which] provide a reader benefit (MacCabe and Snyder 2005: 453).

Consequently, to differentiate high-quality journals, the ‘SJR’ second generation indicator was used. The SJR-2 “covers most of the journals included in the Thomson Reuters Web of Science (WoS) and more” (Guerrero and Moyanegon 2012: 675). Most importantly, its database has 22,878 journals. Further, in many cases where a journal was suspected to be a subscription one –based on the familiarity with its title- but did not appear in SJR-2 database, it was double-checked by visiting the direct journal website. In 100% of cases, a confirming statement that the journal was a free open access one was found. With this rigorous condition, it was not surprising that 80% of the articles were excluded leaving the 120 articles. These articles were acquired through the available databases and through direct ordering from the library e-resources service. First, the abstracts of all articles were examined, and in some cases, the whole article was reviewed to determine if the research was in the international business context or any other field. Then they were grouped into five categories, International Business, Pedagogy, Psychology, Military and Other.

Results and Discussion

This section will start by examining the distribution of CQ articles across different contexts/ disciplines. Please see table 1 below. Later there will be two sub-sections to synthesize the results of two groups of statistical tests. The first treated CQ as a dependent variable while the second treated CQ as an independent variable. For a full list of all articles and tests used in this SR, please see table 2 below.

As expected, the majority of articles were in the International Business context (44%) followed by pedagogy, mostly IB courses.

Table 1: Distribution of articles across contexts

Context	Number	Percentage
Intl Business	53	44%
IB Pedagogy	29	24%

Psychology	11	9%	Other	21	18%
Military	6	5%	Total	120	100%

Table 2: Empirical Tests of CQ in IB

#	Author/s	Publication Year	Sample Size	CQ as Independent / Dependent	Tests Count	Support Count
1	Ang et al.	2007	794	Independent	12	10
2	Ang, S. & Inkpen, A.	2008	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
3	Crowne, K.	2008	140	Dependent	4	3
4	Elenkov, D. & Manev, I.	2009	848	Independent	2	1
5	Gregory et al.	2009	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	Imai, L. & Gelfand, M.	2010	386	Independent	4	2
7	Lee, L. & Sukoco, B.	2010	218	Independent	3	2
8	Moon, T.	2010	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
9	Ramalu et al.	2010	332	Both	20	19
10	Rose et al.	2010	332	Independent	12	3
11	Chen et al.	2011	382	Independent	8	7
12	Groves, K. & Feyerherm, A.	2011	420	Independent	2	2
13	Chen et al.	2012	305	Independent	1	1
14	Kim, Y. & Van Dyne, L.	2012	622	Both	2	2
15	Moon et al.	2012	190	Both	24	15
16	Nafie, W.	2012	280	Independent	4	4
17	Rehg et al.	2012	110	Dependent	9	6
18	Scholz, T.	2012	180	Independent	2	1
19	Chen, M. and Lin, C.	2013	298	Independent	4	3
20	Collins, R. and Kriz, A.	2013	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
21	Huff, K.	2013	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
22	Lee et al.	2013	156	Independent	3	3
23	Li et al.	2013	294	Dependent	2	2
24	Magnusson et al.	2013	62	Independent	2	2
25	Malek, M. & Budhwar, P.	2013	134	Independent	6	6
26	Moon et al.	2013	165	Dependent	22	15
27	Moon, T.	2013	327	Independent	1	1
28	Nakhaei et al.	2013	273	Independent	4	3
29	Sahin et al.	2013	241	Independent	4	1
30	Wood, E. and Peters, H.	2013	42	Dependent	4	3
31	Yitmen, I.	2013	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
32	Zhang, Y.	2013	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
33	Zhao et al.	2013	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
34	Altememi et al.	2014	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
35	Anvari et al.	2014	310	Independent	4	4
36	Bucker et al.	2014	225	Independent	3	3
37	Du Plessis & Barkhuizen, N.	2014	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
38	Huff et al.	2014	154	Both	9	3
39	Konanahalli et al.	2014	191	Independent	3	3
40	Charoensukmongkol, P.	2015	129	Independent	3	3
41	Guomundsottir, S.	2015	178	Independent	12	8

42	Jyoti, J. and Kour, S.	2015	219	Independent	2	2
43	Tuan, L.	2015	409	Independent	1	1
44	Charoensukmongkol, P.	2016	129	Independent	2	1
45	Froese et al.	2016	148	Independent	1	1
46	Lima et al.	2016	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
47	Presbitero, A.	2016	223	Independent	12	12
48	Alshaibani, E. & Bakir, A.	2016	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
49	Le et al.	2016	462	Independent	1	1
50	Ramsey et al.	2016	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
51	Abdolshah et al.	2016	103	N/A	N/A	N/A
52	Bergh, R. & Du Plessis, Y.	2016	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
53	Tuan, T.	2016	392	Independent	8	8

This high percentage of empirical research in the international business context confirms the importance of CQ theory and its valuable applications for MNCs as they mainly conduct business across nations and thus cultures. It was also interesting to check the distribution of research in terms of publication year and size of samples. Please see table 3 and figure 2.

Table 3: Articles publication and sample size

Year	Articles	Samples	Percentage	
2007	1	794	2%	7%
2008	2	140	4%	1%
2009	2	848	4%	7%
2010	5	332	9%	3%
2011	2	802	4%	7%
2012	6	1687	11%	15%
2013	15	2582	28%	22%
2014	6	1559	11%	14%
2015	4	1064	8%	9%
2016	10	1687	19%	15%
Total	53	11495	100%	100%

Although there were no previous SRs that tested the natural development of theory –call it a ‘theory life’- this analysis is included in the hope it becomes a scholarly custom in future SRs. However, it should be noted that this presentation here suffers from two limitations that it only covers the period (January 2007 to September 2016) which unfortunately does not shed light on the early stages of the theory inception. It is also limited to CQ in IB.

Figure 2: Number of articles and samples size

Please note it was very logical to see a peak in research (both articles and samples) after the validation of CQS in 2007, but the unanswered question is that: why did the research peak take place after 5 years of CQS validation? Unfortunately, it is beyond the scope of this paper to answer this question. Moreover, the limitations of the analysis here do not even guess an answer. However, it was unsurprising, to see that the samples size over the period (2007 – 2016) correlated with the distribution of research articles over the same period but with varying differences during the early years (2007 – 2011). It can be noticed the amount of research, and the sampling population around the peak point (2012-2014) were almost symmetrical.

This is another unintended insight on CQ ‘theory life’ that should be considered with great caution and invite other theory-based SRs to investigate. It could also be argued that research results during this peak period are more generalizable due to extensive testing. Finally, it seems that after two years of the first peak, CQ research regained momentum in 2016. Once again

this limited view cannot provide any sufficient answer to this phenomenon that could be native to the case of CQ or possibly generalizable to other theories. Please note that such analysis requires more than one SR but may hold answers to important epistemological questions on the nature of science.

CQ - Dependent Variable

A total of 222 quantitative tests were extracted, out of which, 67 (30%) treated CQ as a *dependent* variable. Out of those only 8 treated CQ as one whole variable rather than four different variables, i.e., metacognitive, cognitive, motivational and behavioral. To facilitate the assessment of the independent variables affecting CQ, three groups were created: Cultural Exposure (33), Personal Traits (15), Cultural Training (11) and a fourth marginal group of ‘Others’ (8). Please see tables 4, 5 and 6 next.

Table 4: Effects of Cultural Exposure on CQ

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	7	21%	6 86%
Cognitive	7	21%	6 86%
Motivational	6	18%	3 50%
Behavioral	6	18%	3 50%
All dimensions	7	21%	5 71%
Total Support	33	100%	23 70%

Table 5: Effects of Personal Traits on CQ

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive		13%	100%
	2		2 %
Cognitive	4	27%	2 50%
Motivational	4	27%	3 75%
Behavioral	4	27%	2 50%
All dimensions	1	07%	1 100%
			1 %
Total Support	15	100%	10 67%

Table 6: Effects of Cultural Training on CQ

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	2	18%	1 50%
Cognitive		27%	100%
	3		3 %
Motivational	3	27%	2 67%
Behavioral	3	27%	2 67%
Total Support	11	100%	10 73%

It was a bit of a surprise to see that ‘Cultural Training’ effects exceeded those of ‘Cultural Exposure’ and ‘Personal Traits.’ Despite being the least tested, ‘Cultural Training’ stood as the most influential

variable affecting CQ. A possible explanation for the lower effect of ‘Cultural Exposure’ could be that different types and the level of exposure to another different culture/s have different effects on CQ and that “some cultural exposures are more significant than others” (Crowne 2008: 393). For example, Moon et al. (2012: 285) concluded, previous international *non-work* rather than work experience and *comprehensiveness* rather than the length of pre-departure cross-cultural training were more positively related to CQ. It should be noted that these results have direct implications on CQ training especially within IB curriculum and executive training.

CQ - Independent Variable

As mentioned earlier 222 tests were extracted, among which 155 (70%) treated CQ as an *independent* variable. Out of those only 35 treated CQ as one whole variable. After computing the results of all 155 tests, unsurprisingly, the total empirical support for CQ stood at 74%. Please see table 7 below. This is far more than the 47% received by the TCE, “a theory of such prominence and disciplinary-spanning power” in international business (David and Han 2004: 51).

Table 7: Total Support for CQ

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	29	19%	22 76%
Cognitive	28	18%	15 54%
Motivational	32	21%	26 81%
Behavioral	31	20%	23 74%
All dimensions	35	23%	29 83%
Total Support	155	100%	115 74%

When breaking down this result, it is noticed that the most supported variable is the motivational dimension and the least is the cognitive dimension. This is a stunning fact given the wider assumption that people usually rely on the acquired knowledge about certain culture to effectively adapt and manage in that culture. The above finding clearly tells us that knowledge by itself is not enough but our internal drive to invest time and energy in learning about the certain culture and use that knowledge to effectively function is what matters. Further, the highest support (83%) for CQ when tested as one whole variable also indicates that CQ dimensions work in an integral way rather than independent capabilities.

However, although this answered the second question, it also posed new questions, i.e., where CQ has the most and least effects and among the four dimensions, which one has the greatest and least effect on which dependent variable. To answer these new questions that will deepen our understanding of CQ effects in the international business context, first the most tested dependent variables were identified, and the levels of support for CQ dimensions were checked with each of them. The most tested dependent variables had in total 97 tests (62%). These were professional performance (37), general adjustment (23), work adjustment (19) and interaction adjustment (18). The overall support for CQ with these variables stood at 70% where CQ had the greatest effect 83% on general adjustment and the least effect on professional performance 59% (Table 8). Please note under professional performance we included tasks, assignments, and any other work-related performance.

Table 8: CQ support for most tested variables

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
P-Performance	37	38%	22 59%
G-Adjustment	23	24%	19 83%
W-Adjustment	19	20%	13 68%
I-Adjustment	18	19%	14 78%
Total Support	97	100%	68 70%

*Where P: Professional; G: General; W: Work; and I: Interaction.

Given the high support for general adjustment and relatively low support for professional performance, future research is encouraged to investigate a mediating model for the relationship between cultural intelligence and these two variables. Next, the effects of each of CQ dimensions on the most tested variables separately were checked.

Table 9: CQ Effects on Professional Performance

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	9	24%	7 78%
Cognitive	8	22%	2 25%
Motivational	9	24%	4 44%
Behavioral	8	22%	6 75%
All dimensions	3	8%	3 100%
Total Support	37	100%	22 59%

Please note that professional performance was most tested by both the metacognitive and motivational

dimensions, but was most supported by the metacognitive and behavioral dimensions. Once again the highest support –although with the least number of tests- confirms our argument on the integral nature of CQ capabilities. The same result is repeated for all three types of adjustment, general, work and interaction. Please see tables 10, 11 and 12.

Table 10: CQ Effects on General Adjustment

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	4	17%	3 75%
Cognitive	4	17%	2 50%
Motivational	5	22%	5 100%
Behavioral	5	22%	4 80%
All dimensions	5	22%	5 100%
Total Support	23	100%	19 83%

Table 11: CQ Effects on Work Adjustment

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	4	21%	2 50%
Cognitive	3	16%	2 67%
Motivational	4	21%	4 100%
Behavioral	5	26%	3 60%
All dimensions	3	16%	2 67%
Total Support	19	100%	13 68%

Table 12: CQ Effects on Interaction Adjustment

CQ Dimensions	Tests	Frequency	Supported
Metacognitive	3	17%	2 67%
Cognitive	3	17%	1 33%
Motivational	4	22%	4 100%
Behavioral	5	28%	4 80%
All dimensions	3	17%	3 100%
Total Support	18	100%	14 78%

Once again the motivational dimension was the most supported among CQ four dimensions with stunning 100% support for work, interaction and general adjustments. The least supported dimension in all tests was the cognitive dimension with 25% for professional performance, 33% for interaction adjustment, 50% for general adjustment and 67% for work adjustment. These results have direct implications for MNCs and their expats. Accordingly, MNCs are strongly encouraged to:

- Incorporate CQ topics in their induction training of new expats.
- Allow expats to experience balanced exposure between work related and non-work related issues.
- Stimulate the drive within the new expats to learn and use the newly learned knowledge to effectively function in the host culture.

Limitations and Recommendations

The academic rigor of the method comes at a cost. First, the SR is limited to articles from subscription journals. Second, the empirical assessment of CQ support is limited to the international business context after 2007. Finally, the in-depth analysis covers only the most tested dependent variables – professional performance, general adjustment, work adjustment and interaction adjustment- whereas CQ is also known to have effects on other important variables, i.e., cross-cultural negotiations and leadership. It is recommended that future studies further investigate what leads to higher CQ with a specific focus on the motivational and the cognitive dimensions, being the most and least influential respectively. Further, given the evidence on the effects of cultural training, it is also recommended to further test the effects of different types and methods of cultural training on CQ. Finally, a replica of this SR can investigate CQ in international business education and executive training.

Originality and Contributions

In trying to answer two questions on the extent of CQ research and support in the international business context, deeper questions on what leads to higher CQ, where CQ is most and least supported and among CQ dimensions, which one had the greatest and least effects on which dependent variable was also answered. In taking the hard way of using GS database, a solid example of how to make use of GS higher coverage while figuring out solutions to its problems, i.e., undifferentiated and repeated results was provided. The paper adequately defended each step of its replicable method to assert the rigor but

also unintentionally provided insights on the natural development of CQ theory. This allowed putting forward an argument with great caution that research results during the peak period are more generalizable due to extensive testing.

Conclusion

With the large volume of undifferentiated research in terms of quality, scope, and context and with the debate on CQ operationalization in the international business context, a systematic review was absolutely needed to clear the clouds. Not only does such high-quality method quantify results of quantitative methods, but it also synthesizes powerful evidence and deepens our knowledge. The results of the replicable empirical assessment suggest that despite criticism, CQ theory remains an important breakthrough in 3C research with practical applications, particularly in international business.

Multinational corporations in dealing with continuing global complexities have an obligation to nurture their CQ capabilities. Different experiences affecting CQ can be grouped under three headings, ‘Cultural Exposure,’ ‘Personal Traits’ and ‘Cultural Training.’ Surprisingly, despite being the least tested, cultural training is the most influential variable affecting CQ level. Further, it is the previous international non-work rather than work experience and comprehensiveness rather than the length of pre-departure cross-cultural training that is more positively related to CQ. Finally, the cultural knowledge by itself is not enough without the drive to use that knowledge to effectively adapt and function across different cultures. To have a high level of CQ expats need to improve and use all four dimensions. That is only an integral CQ can deliver the best results.

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